

Significance of Geography in Depression: A Comparative Study of Older Adults in Rural and Urban Parts of Nepal

Pralhad Adhikari*

Abstract

Older adults are vulnerable to depression because of their old age and other impairments (such as physical, cognitive, and social) invited by it. In Nepal, 44.3% of rural older adults and 34.8% of urban older adults are found to have depression. This study, using secondary data collected for research projects conducted in 2021 and 2023, aimed to determine if human geography (specifically, rural-urban living) affected depression in 746 Nepali older adults. Moreover, it examined if some sociodemographic factors predicted it. The original studies collected data using survey methods from a rural municipality in Kavrepalanchok and a metropolis from Kathmandu. The findings showed that urban-rural living did not significantly affect depression among Nepali older adults, with $t(744)=1.91$ and $p=0.057$ overall, but some symptoms of it (such as anhedonia, emptiness-feeling, apathy, low mood, helplessness, cognitive decline, hopelessness, and low energy) were significantly affected. Some demographic factors like education, socioeconomic status, marital status, and income significantly predicted depression among older adults. The conclusion is that social factors are responsible for mental health problems of older adults as predicted by the biopsychosocial model even though urban-rural living (a human geographical factor) was not seen as affecting depression as a whole. The interventions designed to alleviate depression in older adults should heed selective social factors such as having income and literacy, besides biological and psychological ones. If depression as a whole is considered, urban-rural interventions can be the same but if its symptoms are considered, they need to be discriminating.

Keywords: Depression, older adults, Nepal, rural, urban, human geography

Depression in Older Adults

Depression is one of the leading mental health problems and major causes of disability among older adults in the world. It is a mood disorder and low, anxious, and empty mood persistence for at least two weeks (National Institute on Aging, 2021). Persons prone to depression in younger

* Assistant Professor (Psychology) and Head Department of Psychology and Philosophy,
Tri Chandra Multiple College, Kathmandu
pralhad.adhikari@gmail.com

age tend to be depressed in old age also. Persons suffering from depression may feel hopeless, helpless, worthless, guilty, restless, irritable, and disinterested in things they enjoyed in the past. Their sleep and appetite get disturbed. Older adults with depression have difficulty staying still and concentrating, feel confused and their mental condition is complicated by physical illnesses (Bruce, 2022; Haigh et al., 2018), grief of loss of loved ones, and dementia (Royal College of Psychiatrists, 2024). There are bad consequences of prolonged depression because depressed older adults may be disabled and feel suicidal (Rodda et al., 2011).

In Nepal, depression in older adults has been reported from very low prevalence to very high, for example, 25.5%-60.6% in community samples (Thapa et al., 2018). In recent studies, in the urban part, it was reported that 34.8% of older adults were depressed (Adhikari, 2024). In the rural part, 44.3% of older adults were depressed (Adhikari & McLaren, 2023). The difference in the prevalence of depression is not enough. So, their significance in mean difference has been tested in this study.

Causes of Depression

Functional impairment and social support from family and friends were seen to predict depression (Adhikari & McLaren, 2023). Loneliness and social isolation are two factors that induce depression (World Health Organization, 2023). Being female and being unpartnered are some causes of depression (Bruce, 2022).

Human geographical factors may also cause depression. In this study, rural-urban living has been taken as a geographical factor. It aimed to examine if rural-urban living affected depression among older adults. It also assessed if other demographic factors predicted depression.

The biopsychosocial model of mental health posits that social factors, in addition to biological and psychological factors, contribute to mental health. This theory is the framework for this study. Though testing all predictions of this model is beyond the scope of this study, a prediction that social factors determine mental health problems was tested.

Statement of Problem

Depression is a major challenge among mental health problems, especially during old age. Still, the identification of its determinants is an understudied domain. This study attempted to determine if some social factors like urban-rural living, age, sex, and income determined depression. This study emerges against the backdrop of a stereotype that rural settings are friendlier to the mental health of older adults and this study can clarify such misconceptions.

Significance of Research

The study is significant because the findings can clear up the misconception that urban life is especially unfriendly to the mental health of older adults. Moreover, it can contribute to the theories of depression. For example, the biopsychosocial model posits that biological, psychological, and

social risk factors trigger depression. Rural-urban living can be considered a social factor or factor relevant to human geography which seeks to understand the interaction of human systems with space (Tredinnick, 2024). Moreover, the findings can inform the interventions aimed to reduce mental problems in older adults and policies that target to enhance their mental well-being.

Objectives

The aims of this study were to determine if rural-urban living determined depression among older adults and some demographic factors predicted it. The related hypotheses are given below:

H₁: Rural-urban living (geographic living difference) affects depression (and its symptoms) among older adults.

H₂: Demographic factors like age, sex, marital status, literacy, socioeconomic status, and income predict depression.

Methods

Participants

There were a total of 746 participants in this study from both urban and rural parts of Nepal. The following Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of various characteristics of participants. The rural part refers to Bethanchok Rural Municipality in Kavre district and it is in the mid-hills of Nepal. The urban part refers to Kathmandu Metropolitan City and is located in a valley in the hilly region of Nepal.

Table 1

Characteristics of Participants

		N	%
Geography			
	Rural	300	40.2
	Urban	446	59.8
Sex			
	NA	1	0.1
	Female	350	46.9
	Male	395	52.9
Marital Status			
	NA	1	0.1
	Married	535	71.7
	Single	210	28.2
Literacy			
	Illiterate	104	13.9

	Literate	642	86.1
Income			
	No	310	41.6
	Yes	436	58.4

Note. NA means “not answered”

The following Figure 1 shows the division of participants’ socio-economic status (SES). The majority of them belonged to the middle class.

Figure 1

Socio-economic Status of Participants

Measures

The Nepali translation of the Geriatric Depression Scale (Sheikh & Yesavage, 1986) was used to collect data. It was translated for a research project conducted in 2021 (Adhikari & McLaren, 2023; McLaren & Adhikari, 2023) in a rural municipality of Kavrepalanchok and used in another study in 2023 in Kathmandu Metropolitan City (Adhikari, 2024). In addition, some demographic factors, common to both research projects, were also extracted.

Procedure

Data were collected by survey method in two research projects conducted in 2021 and 2023 (Adhikari, 2024; Adhikari & McLaren, 2023). In both projects, older adults above 59 participated. They were approached at their residence or locality and informed about the purpose of the studies. Then they consented to participate. Data were collected by research assistants, who asked the questions to older adults. The data used in this paper were secondary.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Jamovi 2.6 and SPSS 27. Descriptives were used to summarize data. A t-test for independent means was used to test the significance of the mean difference. Regression analysis was used to test a prediction model. Two graphs were created to illustrate the results.

Results

Descriptives

The following Table 2 shows the descriptives for depression. The results show that mean depression was higher among rural older adults than urban older adults. The following norms can be used to classify the scores of depression if future studies use the same scale used in this study: Scores below Q_1 =No depression, Scores between Q_1 and Q_2 =Low Depression, Scores between Q_2 and Q_3 =High Depression, and Scores above Q_3 =Very High Depression.

Table 2

Descriptives of Depression in Older Adults

Group	N	Mean	Q_1	Q_2	Q_3	SD
Rural	300	5.38	3	5	7	2.89
Urban	446	4.92	2	4	7	3.44
All	746	5.11	3	5	7	3.24

The following Figure 2 shows that mean depression was fairly higher for rural older adults than urban older adults.

Figure 2

Measures of Central Tendency for Depression of Older Adults

T-test for Independent Means

A t-test for independent means showed that geography (urban vs. rural) did not have an effect on depression, $t(744)=1.91$, $p=0.057$. The significant difference in means was examined for each item as seen in the Table 3 below. For all items except a few, there was a significant difference in means between older adults in rural and urban parts. For example, the mean satisfaction with life was higher,

and the mean emptiness of life was lesser for urban older adults than rural older adults. Older adults in rural and urban settings do not differ significantly in terms of uncertainty about the future (item 6), lack of outdoor activities (item 9), worthlessness (item 12), and upward comparison (item 15). There is a pattern in reverse-scored items marked by the smiley emoji (☺)– older adults in the urban municipality had far higher mean scores than those in the rural municipality. It means the quality of life is very high in urban parts of the country for older adults. In the majority of items that indicate mental distress, rural older adults had higher mean scores. The depressive symptoms of fearfulness, worthlessness, social withdrawal, and low comparative self-worth were not significantly affected by rural-urban living. This geographic factor significantly affected the other depressive symptoms: anhedonia, feeling empty, apathy, low mood, helplessness, cognitive decline, hopelessness, and low energy.

Table 3

Item-wise Comparison Using t-test

No	Item	Statistic	p	Rural		Urban	
				M	SD	M	SD
1	☺ Are you basically satisfied with your life?	-35 .6316 ^a	<.001	0.0567	0.232	0.866	0.342
2	Have you dropped many of your activities and interests?	-2.7060 ^a	0.007	0.5567	0.498	0.656	0.476
3	Do you feel that your life is empty?	5 .2252 ^a	<.001	0.4233	0.495	0.243	0.429
4	Do you often get bored?	4.9276 ^a	<.001	0.520	0.500	0.340	0.474
5	☺ Are you in good spirits most of the time?	-20.6267 ^a	<.001	0.1367	0.344	0.755	0.431
6	Are you afraid that something bad is going to happen to you ?	-0.4065	0.685	0.4	0.491	0.415	0.493
7	☺ Do you feel happy most of the time?	-21.7851 ^a	<.001	0.1133	0.318	0.752	0.432
8	Do you often feel helpless?	3.0864 ^a	0.002	0.25	0.434	0.158	0.365
9	Do you prefer to stay at home, rather than going out and doing new things?	0.095	0.924	0.48	0.5	0.476	0.5
10	Do you feel you have more problems with memory than most?	5 .8438 ^a	<.001	0.7467	0.436	0.538	0.499
11	☺ Do you think it is wonderful to be alive now?	-24.2032 ^a	<.001	0.2	0.401	0.868	0.339
12	Do you feel pretty worthless the way you are now?	1.7291 ^a	0.084	0.2367	0.426	0.184	0.388
13	☺ Do you feel full of energy?	-3.0452 ^a	0.002	0.4733	0.5	0.587	0.493
14	Do you feel that your situation is hopeless?	3.7719 ^a	<.001	0.3033	0.46	0.184	0.388
15	Do you think that most people are better off than you are?	-0.1033	0.918	0.4867	0.501	0.491	0.501

Note. Insignificant items are bolded in p-value; ☺ means items are reverse scored (so, they measure quality of life).

Regression Analysis

The regression model with six demographic factors as independent variables and depression as a dependent variable was tested and found significant, $F(7, 737)=9.46$, $p<0.001$. In it, 8.24% variance was explained by six predictors. The following Table 4 shows that marital status, income, literacy, and socioeconomic status significantly predicted depression in older adults. Age and sex could not predict it.

The coefficient for being unpartnered compared to partnered is 0.354, which is significant ($p < .001$). This suggests that being unpartnered is associated with a 0.354 unit increase in depression. Being literate (compared to illiterate) is associated with a significant decrease (-0.3537, $p < .001$) in depression, indicating that literate individuals have lower scores on depression compared to illiterate ones.

Those with income (compared to those without) show a significant decrease of -0.2679 units in the depression ($p < .001$). This suggests that having an income is associated with lower values of depression. Being poor compared to the middle class is associated with a significant increase of 0.4009 units ($p = 0.002$). This indicates that poorer individuals tend to have higher scores on depression than middle-class individuals. Being rich compared to the middle-class shows no significant effect ($\beta = -0.0584$, $p = 0.694$), suggesting no meaningful difference between these groups.

Table 4

Sociodemographic Predictors of Depression in Older Adults

Predictor	SE	t	p	β
Intercept ^a	1.186	4.209	<.001	
Sex:				
Male – Female	0.2335	-1.835	0.067	-0.1324
Marital Status:				
Unpartnered – Partnered	0.2732	4.195	<.001	0.354
Education:				
Literate – Illiterate	0.331	-3.459	<.001	-0.3537
Having Income:				
Yes – No	0.2371	-3.657	<.001	-0.2679
SES:				
Poor – Middle-class	0.4221	3.074	0.002	0.4009
Rich – Middle-class	0.4802	-0.394	0.694	-0.0584
Age	0.0172	1.209	0.227	0.0456

Note.^a Represents reference level

Discussion

Interpretation of Results

Despite the differential prevalence of depression between older adults of rural and urban parts, a significant difference was not found in depression between them. Neither are fearfulness, social withdrawal, and worthlessness. However, anhedonia, emptiness-feeling, apathy, low mood, helplessness, cognitive decline, hopelessness, and low energy were significantly affected.

Findings are somewhat contrary to expectations. Villages in Nepal are still believed to be collectivistic. Nevertheless, a higher prevalence of depression in the village means that the village life is not as safe for older adults as assumed. Depression is not caused by a single factor alone but multiple factors, in a complicated way, trigger the onset or grip of the mental health problem. Older adults living in rural parts are free to move but they may be unable to because of functional impairment, for example. There may be several other constraints like lack of access to healthcare institutions, market, and income, among others. Other causes may be loss of financial grip (an indicator of control), declining social support and increasing hopelessness as their time on the earth seems running out.

In the case of city older adults, they may be prone to depression because of emotional and social loneliness. Moreover, they may lose their financial hold. Besides, they may not be able to be creative regarding how to spend a retired life unlike rural older adults, most of whom can choose to live in nature and till the land to different degrees because most families are still based on agriculture and possess pieces of land.

Some factors like having income, literacy, being or not being partnered, and socioeconomic status predicted depression. Income is important because it is related to financial control. Nepal government gives old age allowance after 68 years of age. If older adults from 60 to 68 can have some source of income, they may not fall prey to depression as quickly.

Comparison with Past Studies

Sex did not affect depression among older adults in this study like in an urban sample (Gorkhali & Karki, 2024). Age was not associated with it significantly unlike a sample of the Rai (Chalise & Rai, 2013). Social factors like literacy predicted depression in this study like in the past studies (see Khanal et al., 2024). A previous study had shown that depression is not significantly associated with urban-rural living (Gaire et al., 2021) but another study showed that urban-rural residence can significantly predict depression (Manandhar et al., 2019). This study also showed that some discrete symptoms were significantly affected by urban-rural living. For example, anhedonia, emptiness-feeling, low mood, hopelessness, cognitive decline, helplessness, and fatigue/low energy were significantly affected by this factor.

Limitations and Strengths

This study compared rural and urban samples that belonged to Bagmati province. The comparison may not tell the whole story about other provinces. So, the results should be cautiously evaluated. The sample does not represent the topographic diversity. The common demographic factors were limited. If primary data had been collected, more factors could have been examined for determinants.

This study had a large sample size with a sizable number in both rural and urban categories. So, the comparison was potent. Moreover, the norm established by this study may be more valid than previous studies. Moreover, this study has contributed to the sociocultural perspective. Overall, depression was not affected by urban-rural living but its many individual symptoms were significantly affected.

Implications

This study supports a prediction of the biopsychosocial model that social factors (such as SES, income, and literacy) contribute to the emergence or maintenance of mental health problems even though the main factor considered in this study urban-rural living did not affect depression as a whole. Other demographic factors are seen to be determining. Nonetheless, various aspects of depression were affected by urban-rural geographic living, too.

Rural-urban living did not affect depression. It means the interventions aimed to alleviate depression can be evenly planned and executed in both living conditions— urban and rural. However, if a particular aspect of depression needs to be addressed, the urban-rural difference should be accounted for. The findings from this study can inform the policies made to enhance well-being of older adults. For example, they can plan to launch similar programs for the mental health of older adults in rural and urban parts by reducing depression overall. However, discriminating interventions are clearly seen as necessary, if we are to look at results related to discrete depressive symptoms.

Future Research

There are various aspects related to geography but this study was limited to only one aspect. Future studies can investigate if the topographic factors like living in mountains, hills, and terai plains affect depression. Likewise, depression may be affected by zonal factors. So, clusters of ethnicity, language, caste, and socioeconomic factors may be tested as predictors in the future. The studies can spread to mountainous (Himali) and plain (Taraii) parts of Nepal beyond the hilly (Pahadi) parts as covered in this study.

Conclusion

The conclusion is that rural-urban living does not significantly affect depression as a whole among older adults in Nepal. Nonetheless, human geography, in relation to other unexplored variables, may matter in depression. Other social factors like education, SES, having income, and (not) having

a partner are capable of predicting depression. Human geographical factors need to be considered while making the policies and interventions. The interventions designed to reduce depression as a whole should not discriminate between rural or urban parts. Nevertheless, if specific aspects of depression are considered, there should be discriminating interventions.

References

- Adhikari, P. (2024). *Municipal responsibility for mental health of older adults: Their expectations in the context of loneliness because of children's emigration*. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/14IH7EmaEFYNxL8ISoB5ramQZMEF54HW8/view?usp=sharing>
- Adhikari, P., & McLaren, S. (2023). Functional Impairment and Depressive Symptoms among Older Adults of Rural Nepal: The Moderating Role of Three Sources of Social Support. *Clinical Gerontologist, 46*(5), 832–843. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317115.2023.2187732>
- Bruce, D. F. (2022). *Depression in Older People: Symptoms, Causes, Treatments*. <https://www.webmd.com/depression/depression-elderly>
- Chalise, H. N., & Rai, S. L. (2013). Prevalence and Correlates of Depression among Nepalese Rai Older Adults. *Journal of Gerontology & Geriatric Research, 2*(4). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2167-7182.1000130>
- Gaire, D., Gahatraj, N. R., Yadav, R. K., Shah, G., & Baral, S. (2021). Study among geriatric people residing in urban and rural areas and associated factor with depression in Nepal. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health, 8*(9), 4167. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20213514>
- Gorkhali, B., & Karki, N. (2024). Anxiety and depression in elderly people living in an urban community in Kathmandu. *Janaki Medical College Journal of Medical Science, 12*(01), 4–11. <https://www.nepjol.info/index.php/JMCJMS/article/download/65233/49510>
- Haigh, E. A. P., Bogucki, O. E., Sigmon, S. T., & Blazer, D. G. (2018). Depression among older adults: A 20-year update on five common myths and misconceptions. *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry, 26*(1), 107–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jagp.2017.06.011>
- Khanal, G., Selvamani, Y., Thapa, S., & Chinnaiyan, S. (2024). Prevalence and covariates of depression among older adults in Nepal: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLOS Mental Health, 1*(4), e0000112. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmen.0000112>
- Manandhar, K., Risal, A., Shrestha, O., Manandhar, N., Kunwar, D., Koju, R., & Holen, A. (2019). Prevalence of geriatric depression in the Kavre district, Nepal: Findings from a cross sectional community survey. *BMC Psychiatry, 19*(1), 271. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-019-2258-5>

- McLaren, S., & Adhikari, P. (2023). Hope and Suicidal Ideation among Older Adults Living in the Rural Mid-Hills of Nepal. *Clinical Gerontologist*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07317115.2023.2274049>
- National Institute on Aging. (2021). *Depression and Older Adults*. <https://www.nia.nih.gov/health/mental-and-emotional-health/depression-and-older-adults>
- Rodda, J., Walker, Z., & Carter, J. (2011). Depression in older adults. *BMJ*, *343*, d5219. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d5219>
- Royal College of Psychiatrists. (2024). *Depression in older adults*. <https://www.rcpsych.ac.uk/mental-health/mental-illnesses-and-mental-health-problems/depression-in-older-adults>
- Sheikh, J. I., & Yesavage, J. A. (1986). 9/geriatric depression scale (Gds) recent evidence and development of a shorter version. *Clinical Gerontologist*, *5*(1–2), 165–173. https://doi.org/10.1300/J018v05n01_09
- Thapa, D. K., Visentin, D., Kornhaber, R., & Cleary, M. (2018). Prevalence of mental disorders among older people in Nepal: A systematic review. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal*, *16*(62), 181–190. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30636762/>
- Tredinnick, K. (2024). *Human Geography For Dummies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- World Health Organization. (2023). *Mental health of older adults*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-health-of-older-adults>

ISSN: 2795-1650

त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय

त्रिवि
वार्षिक दिवस प्रकाशन
TU Annual Publication

प्रकाशक : त्रिवि, सूचना तथा जनसम्पर्क महाशाखा, कीर्तिपुर
फोन नं. : ०१-४३३०३४६
फ्याक्स : ९७७-१-४३३९२६४
Email : info@tu.edu.np
Website : www.tu.edu.np
कम्प्युटर डिजाइन : सरोज महर्जन
मुद्रक : त्रिवि, छापाखाना, कीर्तिपुर, फोन नं. ४३३९३२०

Follow us !

त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय
वार्षिक दिवस प्रकाशन - २०८२
प्रकाशन समिति

प्रा.डा. दुबि नन्द ढकाल शिक्षाध्यक्ष, त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय	संयोजक
डा. लक्ष्मी कान्त शर्मा निर्देशक, योजना निर्देशनालय	सदस्य
प्रा.डा. कृष्णप्रसाद न्यौपाने विभागीय प्रमुख, नेपाली केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
प्रा.डा. ध्रुव कार्की विभागीय प्रमुख, अङ्ग्रेजी केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
डा. कर्णस्वर खतिवडा विभागीय प्रमुख, भाषाविज्ञान केन्द्रीय विभाग	सदस्य
श्री लिल्ली थापा क्षेत्री प्रमुख, सूचना तथा जनसम्पर्क महाशाखा	सदस्य-सचिव

२०८२ असार २० गते शुक्रवार

४ जुलाई २०२५

विषयसूची

विषय/लेखक	पृष्ठ
त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयको परीक्षा प्रणालीको वर्तमान अवस्था, चुनौती र सुधारका उपायहरू <i>ताराप्रसाद भुसाल, सुमन खरेल</i>	1
नेपालका मूर्तिकलामा पाइएका शुषिर बाजा <i>परशुरामप्रसाद पौडेल</i>	11
त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयको आर्थिक कार्यप्रणाली र बेरुजु <i>महेन्द्र न्यौपाने, राजेन्द्र खनाल, देवराज आचार्य</i>	27
त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयको सुरक्षा एवम् सुधार र विद्यार्थीका लागि कमाउँदै पढ्दै कार्यक्रम <i>एकात्म आचार्य</i>	38
तबलावादनको विकासमा भारतको योगदान: एक अध्ययन <i>वेङ्कटेश ढकाल</i>	52
त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालयमा आर्थिक अनुशासन र सुधारका पक्ष <i>सविना श्रेष्ठ</i>	63
मानविकी तथा सामाजिक शास्त्र सङ्कायमा सञ्चालित विद्यावारिधि कार्यक्रम <i>सुकुम शर्मा (गोविन्दप्रसाद शर्मा)</i>	75
Design and Environmental Control Strategies for High-Performance Electron Microscopy Laboratory: A Technical Perspective <i>D. Parajuli, B. Paudel</i>	85
Evaluating the Impact of Study Leave Policies on Faculty Development and Retention at Tribhuvan University <i>Hukum Thapa</i>	115
Climate Change Governance and Global South Justice under the Paris Agreement <i>Newal Chaudhary</i>	131
Similarities and Differences between Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine and Scope of Their Integration in Nepal <i>Nirmal Bhusal</i>	149

विषयसूची

विषय/लेखक	पृष्ठ
Significance of Geography in Depression: A Comparative Study of Older Adults in Rural and Urban Parts of Nepal <i>Pralhad Adhikari</i>	159
Learning Science Through Laboratory Teaching Method at Secondary Schools in Nepal <i>Pratima Tamrakar, Narayan Prasad Timilsena, Krishna Maya Devkota</i>	170
Enhancing Data Center Security through Intrusion Detection Systems using Artificial Intelligence <i>Susil Bhatta, Sharad Kumar Ghimire</i>	180
Comparative Analysis of Phytochemical Constituents and Antioxidant Activity of <i>Allium Sativum</i> from Three Geographical Regions <i>Yograj Podar, Sudeep Kanth, Dipesh Pandit, Prabesh Ghimire, Bimala Subba</i>	204